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Left atrial pump strain predicts long-term survival after transcatheter aortic valve implantation

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ABSTRACT

Background: This study aims at investigating left atrial (LA) deformation by left atrial reservoir (LARS) and pump strain (LAPS) and its implications for long-term survival in patients with severe aortic stenosis (AS) undergoing transcatheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI).

Methods: Speckle tracking echocardiography was performed in 198 patients with severe AS undergoing TAVI. Association of strain parameters with cardiovascular mortality was determined.

Results: Over a follow-up time of 5 years, 49 patients (24.7%) died. LAPS was more impaired in non-survivors than survivors ($P = 0.010$), whereas no difference was found for LARS ($P = 0.114$), LA ejection fraction ($P = 0.241$), and LA volume index ($P = 0.292$). Kaplan-Meier analyses yielded a reduced survival probability according to the optimal threshold for LAPS ($P = 0.002$). A more impaired LAPS was associated with increased mortality risk (HR 1.12 [95% CI 1.02–1.22]; $P = 0.014$) independent of LVEF, LAVI, age, and sex. Addition of LAPS improved multivariable echocardiographic (LVEF, LAVI) and clinical (age, sex) models with potential incremental value for mortality prediction ($P = 0.013$ and $P = 0.031$, respectively). In contrast, LARS and LAVI were not associated with mortality.

Conclusions: In patients undergoing aortic valve replacement for severe AS, LAPS was impaired in patients dying during long-term follow-up after TAVI, differentiated survivors from non-survivors, was independently associated with long-term mortality, and yielded potential incremental value for survival prediction after TAVI. LAPS seems useful for risk stratification in severe AS and timely valve replacement.

1. Introduction

Degenerative aortic stenosis (AS) is the most prevalent valvular heart disease in high-income countries with increasing incidence in the ageing population [1]. Definitive treatment includes surgical or transcatheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI), and the interventional approach has improved access to treatment for these mostly elderly patients at increased risk [1,2]. Current guidelines recommend valve replacement depending on AS severity, presence of symptoms, and reduced left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) [1]. The latter, however, only becomes apparent at a late stage when progressive cardiac remodelling may have occurred leading to exhaustion of compensatory mechanisms

and permanent cardiac damage [2–5].

New imaging markers are being investigated to disclose the crucial transition from adaptive to irreversible myocardial remodelling [6,7]. There is solid evidence supporting the use of advanced imaging modalities such as speckle tracking echocardiography (STE) for detecting adverse remodelling and improving the timing of intervention [8–10]. Remodelling of the left ventricle (LV) compensates for the increased afterload occurring in AS and stabilises cardiac output over a long time period [11]. This response may also affect the left atrium (LA) as its function is interconnected with that of the ventricle [2,5,12]. The LA stores blood in the reservoir phase, directs it to the LV during the conduit phase, and pumps it into the LV in the contraction phase [13,14]. Hence,

Abbreviations: AS, Aortic Stenosis; AVA, Aortic Valve Area; LA, Left Atrium; LAEF, Left Atrial Ejection Fraction; LAPS, Left Atrial Pump Strain; LARS, Left Atrial Reservoir Strain; LAVI, Left Atrial Volume Index; LV, Left Ventricle; LVEF, Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction; MTPG, Mean Transaortic Pressure Gradient; STE, Speckle Tracking Echocardiography; TAVI, Transcatheter Aortic Valve Implantation; TTE, Transthoracic Echocardiography.

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the LA contributes to almost a third of ventricular stroke volume, and its function is modulated by systolic ventricular function as well as diastolic pressures [15,16]. In addition to progressive enlargement of the LA, all three components of its function may become impaired in severe AS [13,16]. However, the implications of such alterations for long-term outcome in these patients are not well understood.

The aim of this study was to investigate LA function assessed by LA reservoir strain (LARS) and pump strain (LAPS) and to understand their association with cardiovascular mortality during long-term follow-up after TAVI.

2. Methods

2.1. Study population

Patients with severe AS (aortic valve area (AVA) $< 1 \text{ cm}^2$ or indexed AVA $< 0.6 \text{ cm}^2/\text{m}^2$, and mean transaortic pressure gradient (MTPG) $> 40 \text{ mmHg}$) from the prospective AS registry of the University Heart Center Zurich, Switzerland, were included in this retrospective study after obtaining approval of the local ethics committee and informed consent. Patients were included when a comprehensive echocardiographic examination was available within three months prior to TAVI allowing complete target analyses according to current recommendations [17–19]. Patients were excluded from the study if they were younger than 18 years or if there was concomitant moderate or severe valvular disease, atrial fibrillation or flutter, permanent pacemakers or other cardiac devices.

2.2. Transthoracic echocardiography

Transthoracic echocardiographic (TTE) examinations were performed using commercially available equipment (iE33 or Epiq 7, Philips Medical Systems, The Netherlands; Vivid7 or E9 or E95, GE Healthcare, USA). All echocardiographic measurements were performed by certified specialists according to current recommendations [7,18,19]. LVEF and LA ejection fraction (LAEF) were calculated by Simpson's biplane method [18].

2.3. Speckle tracking echocardiography and strain analysis

TomTec Image Arena Cardiac Performance Analysis (Version 4.6) was applied for offline assessment of LA deformation using two-dimensional STE. Endocardial tracing was performed using dedicated atrial strain mode. Non-foreshortened apical four-chamber (A4C) and two-chamber (A2C) views were used for measuring biplane LA global longitudinal strain (LAS) according to current recommendations [17–19]. LA cycle timing was identified by M-mode. End-diastole was set at the last frame before mitral valve closure and end-systole at the last frame before mitral valve opening [17]. After the three phases of LA deformation had been identified, LAS was reported separately for reservoir (LARS; positive value) and pump (LAPS; negative value) phase. Published LA strain reference values were considered as normal range [20].

2.4. Reproducibility of strain measurements

Strain analysis of 20 echocardiographic examinations was performed by two observers to investigate inter-observer agreement and repeated by the main observer with a difference of 12 months to determine intra-observer agreement using the same software version for all measurements. Concordance correlation coefficient was applied for assessing reproducibility (inter-observer agreement) and repeatability (intra-

observer agreement). These results are reported as supplementary data online (Table S1). There was good to substantial strength of inter- and intra-observer agreement for LA strain measurements [21].

2.5. Follow-up

The date of TTE before TAVI (i.e. within three months prior to procedure) marked the date of study inclusion and the date of TAVI procedure marked the start of follow-up. Cardiovascular mortality was defined as primary endpoint, according to VARC-3 criteria [22]. Patient survival status was assessed from patient records and/or phone calls.

2.6. Statistics

For all statistical analyses, a long-term follow-up of five years (1825 days) was considered with censoring of the patients with a longer follow-up. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to test normality, evidencing that most continuous variables are not normally distributed. Continuous variables are given as median [interquartile range, IQR] and categorical variables as absolute number (percentage). Continuous variables were compared with Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon test, categorical variables with Fisher's exact test. Correlation between continuous variables was tested using Pearson's r or Spearman's ρ correlation coefficient as appropriate. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis was used to determine the optimal threshold for discriminating survivors from non-survivors, and model discrimination was summarised by the area under the curve (AUC). The AUC from models was compared with the DeLong method using *pROC* (version 1.18.0) package. Survival analysis was performed using Kaplan-Meier survival curves and Cox proportional hazard regression; variables were dichotomised at their optimal threshold according to the ROC analysis, or, for some analyses, divided into tertiles. Kaplan-Meier survival curves and Log Rank tests of time-to-event data were analysed with the *survminer* (version 0.4.9) package. Time-dependent associations with cardiovascular mortality were analysed in uni-, bi- and multivariable Cox regression models. Proportional hazard assumptions were assessed for all models using the scaled Schoenfeld residuals, with all included variables meeting the assumption. A sensitivity analysis was performed for the total follow-up time (i.e. without truncation) as well as for all-cause mortality and when patients with low-flow low-gradient AS were excluded. Cox regression analysis of variance (Cox-ANOVA) was used to test model fit. Likelihood ratio test (χ^2) and Harrell's C-statistic were used to examine the incremental value of predictors in the bi- and multivariable models compared to the nested models. Statistical analyses were performed using MedCalc® version 19.6.4 and R version 4.2.0. Statistical significance was set at a two-sided P value < 0.05 .

3. Results

3.1. Baseline characteristics

A total of 198 patients were included. Clinical and echocardiographic baseline characteristics are summarised in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. Symptoms were mostly not severe (NYHA $< \text{III}$) and LVEF was generally preserved (median [IQR]: 59.0% [52.0–65.0]).

3.2. Left atrial size and function

LA size as determined by left atrial volume index (LAVI) was increased in three-quarters (77%) of the study population (43.3 ml/m² [35.3–55.4]) (Table 2). LA function was normal in 76% during the reservoir phase (LARS 21.3% [17.2–25.9]) and in 43% during the

Table 1
Clinical baseline characteristics.

Parameters	Overall (N = 198)	Survivors (N = 166)	Non-survivors (N = 32)	P
Age, years	81 [76.3–84.0]	80 [76.0–84.0]	83 [80.8–86.0]	0.006*
Women, N (%)	92 (46.5)	79 (47.6)	13 (40.6)	0.596
BMI, kg/m ²	26.8 [24.1–29.8]	26.8 [24.2–30.1]	27.1 [23.1–28.2]	0.281
BSA, m ²	1.8 [1.7–1.9]	1.8 [1.7–2.0]	1.8 [1.6–1.9]	0.313
Hypertension, N (%)	151 (76.3)	124 (74.7)	27 (84.4)	0.342
Diabetes, N (%)	49 (24.7)	41 (24.7)	8 (25.0)	1.000
Dyslipidaemia, N (%)	132 (66.7)	114 (68.7)	18 (56.2)	0.246
Clinically relevant CAD, N (%)	121 (61.1)	98 (59.0)	23 (71.9)	0.244
Peripheral artery disease, N (%)	35 (17.7)	29 (17.5)	6 (18.8)	1.000
Cerebrovascular disease, N (%)	39 (19.7)	28 (16.9)	11 (34.4)	0.042*
COPD, N (%)	25 (12.6)	22 (13.3)	3 (9.4)	0.753
eGFR, ml/min/1.73m ²	64.0 [50.0–77.0]	63.0 [49.0–77.0]	64.9 [54.0–78.5]	0.465
NYHA III or IV, N (%)	4 (2.0)	4 (2.4)	0	1.000
EuroSCORE II, %	2.8 [1.7–5.0]	2.7 [1.6–4.4]	3.7 [2.0–7.1]	0.031*
STS-Score, %	3.1 [1.9–5.0]	3.0 [1.9–4.6]	3.8 [2.9–5.6]	0.022*

Continuous variables are given as median [IQR] and categorical variables as number (percentage).

BMI, body mass index; BSA, body surface area; CAD, coronary artery disease; COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate; NYHA, New York Heart Association; EuroSCORE, European System for Cardiac Operative Risk Evaluation; STS-Score, Society of Thoracic Surgeons-Score.

* Significant values ($P < 0.05$).

Table 2
Echocardiographic baseline characteristics.*

Parameters	Overall (N = 198)	Survivors (N = 166)	Non-survivors (N = 32)	P
AVA, cm ²	0.8 [0.6–0.9]	0.8 [0.6–0.9]	0.7 [0.6–0.8]	0.586
AVAI, cm ² /m ²	0.4 [0.4–0.5]	0.4 [0.4–0.5]	0.4 [0.4–0.5]	0.961
MTPG, mmHg	45.0 [36.0–56.0]	45.0 [35.3–56.0]	46.5 [37.8–55.0]	0.777
LVEF, %	59.0 [52.0–65.0]	59.0 [53.0–64.0]	58.0 [49.3–66.3]	0.798
SVI, ml/m ²	39.6 [34.5–44.9]	39.7 [34.8–45.0]	36.9 [31.1–43.7]	0.226
LAEF, %	34.0 [22.6–41.8]	34.6 [23.1–42.7]	30.5 [22.1–36.4]	0.241
LAVI, ml/m ²	43.3 [35.3–55.4]	42.3 [35.1–54.5]	46.8 [38.0–58.6]	0.292
LVMMI, g/m ²	100.0 [83.0–124.8]	99.0 [83.0–124.0]	105.0 [73.0–127.0]	0.868
LV septum, cm	1.2 [1.0–1.3]	1.2 [1.0–1.3]	1.2 [1.1–1.3]	0.855
Subaortic septal hypertrophy, cm (N = 41)	1.4 [1.3–1.5]	1.4 [1.3–1.5]	1.6 [1.3–1.7]	0.517
LV diastolic dysfunction, N (%)				0.104
Grade I	33 (23.1)	29 (23.2)	4 (22.2)	
Grade II	64 (44.8)	59 (47.2)	5 (27.8)	
Grade III	12 (8.4)	8 (6.4)	4 (22.2)	
Indeterminate	34 (23.8)	29 (23.2)	5 (27.8)	
E/A	0.7 [0.6–1.0]	0.7 [0.6–1.0]	0.8 [0.6–1.1]	0.771
E/e' lateral	14.6 [10.2–18.5]	14.6 [10.4–18.9]	12.7 [9.7–16.3]	0.305
E/e' medial	17.4 [12.6–23.0]	17.7 [12.4–23.0]	16.0 [12.8–22.5]	0.673
E/e' average	16.1 [11.7–19.9]	16.3 [12.5–20.4]	12.7 [11.0–19.6]	0.365

Continuous variables are given as median [IQR] and categorical variables as number (percentage).

AVA, aortic valve area; AVAI, aortic valve area index; MTPG, mean transaortic pressure gradient; LVEF, left ventricular ejection fraction; SVI, stroke volume index; LAEF, left atrial ejection fraction; LAVI, left atrial volume index; LVMMI, left ventricular muscle mass index; LV, left ventricle.

* Significant values ($P < 0.05$).

contractile phase (LAPS -9.2% [-11.9 – -6.2]). The concordance correlation coefficient for inter- and intra-observer variability was 0.98 and 0.97 for LARS, respectively, and 0.97 and 0.94 for LAPS, respectively (Supplementary data online, Table S1).

A moderate correlation was found between LARS and LAPS (Pearson's r : -0.64 ; $P < 0.001$). Age and LA deformation revealed weak correlations for both LARS (-0.09 ; $P = 0.227$) and LAPS (0.12 ; $P = 0.097$). Pearson's r and Spearman's ρ showed similar results.

3.3. Survival

Median follow-up duration was 1835 [IQR 1371–2337] days. Over a follow-up time of 5 years, 49 patients (24.7%) died, among which 32 (65.3%) due to a cardiovascular cause. No difference in survival between women and men was observed, while non-survivors were slightly older than survivors (Table 1). AS severity (i.e. AVA and MTPG) was similar between non-survivors and survivors (Table 2). LAPS was more impaired in non-survivors (-7.2% [-9.7 – -5.2]) than survivors (-9.5% [-12.5 – -6.8]; $P = 0.010$; Fig. 1), whereas no difference was found for LARS ($P = 0.114$; Fig. 1), LAEF ($P = 0.241$; Table 2; Fig. 1), and

LAVI ($P = 0.292$; Table 2).

The optimal threshold for LAPS ($> -6.8\%$) discriminated survivors from non-survivors with a sensitivity of 50% and a specificity of 75% (ROC AUC 65%; $P = 0.006$), while that for LARS did not ($\leq 22.6\%$; sensitivity 44%; specificity 78%; ROC AUC 59%; $P = 0.082$). Kaplan-Meier survival analyses differed significantly when the population was dichotomised according to the LAPS threshold (Log Rank $\chi^2 = 9.4$; $P = 0.002$; Fig. 2). Kaplan-Meier survival analyses for LAPS tertiles (tertile 1: -24.3 to -10.9% ; tertile 2: -10.9 to -7.4% ; tertile 3: -7.4 to -1.5%) revealed a significantly higher survival probability for the first tertile compared to the third tertile ($P = 0.008$; Supplementary data online, Fig. S1).

In univariable Cox regression models (Supplementary data online, Table S2), a more impaired LAPS was associated with increased mortality risk (HR 1.12; $P = 0.014$), while LARS was not significantly associated with the endpoint (HR 0.96; $P = 0.130$). Age as a well-established risk factor showed a good association with the endpoint (HR 1.08; $P = 0.017$). The highest model fit (χ^2) and greatest C-index were observed with univariable models for age or LAPS.

In multivariable Cox regression models, the association of LAPS with

Fig. 1. Distribution of key parameters in the overall study population according to 5-year cardiovascular mortality. There was no difference among the study population regarding LAEF (A) or LARS (B), whereas LAPS differed significantly between survivors and non-survivors (C). *Significant values ($P < 0.05$).
LAEF; left atrial ejection fraction; LARS, left atrial reservoir strain; LAPS, left atrial pump strain.

Fig. 2. Comparison of survival probability according to LAPS for 5-year cardiovascular mortality. Kaplan-Meier survival probability of cardiovascular mortality stratified by optimal threshold for LAPS as determined by ROC analysis. P value calculated using Log Rank test.
LAPS, left atrial pump strain.

mortality remained independent of conventional echocardiographic parameters such as LVEF and LAVI as well as of major clinical parameters such as age and sex (Table 3). Multivariable models including clinical parameters yielded the best model fit, with the model including age, sex and LAPS having the highest significance (χ^2 13.31, $\chi^2 P = 0.004$; C-index 0.69 [95% CI 0.59–0.78]; Table 3; Fig. 3).

The fit of multivariable models compared to nested models for the association with mortality was tested with either LARS or LAPS. Model fit did not improve upon inclusion of LARS (data not shown). In comparison to echocardiographic and clinical nested models including LVEF and LAVI (χ^2 0.58, $\chi^2 P = 0.749$) or age and sex (χ^2 8.65, $\chi^2 P = 0.013$), model fit improved significantly upon inclusion of LAPS (ANOVA $P = 0.013$ and ANOVA $P = 0.031$, respectively; Fig. 3).

Sensitivity analyses for total follow-up (i.e. without truncation) as well as for all-cause mortality and for excluding low-flow low-gradient

Table 3
Multivariable Cox regression models for cardiovascular mortality.

Variables	Cox Regression			Harrell's C-statistic	
	HR	95% CI	P	C-index	95% CI
LVEF	0.99	0.97–1.02	0.704	0.57	0.47–0.67
LAVI	1.00	0.98–1.02	0.976		
LARS	0.96	0.91–1.02	0.185		
LVEF	0.99	0.97–1.02	0.675	0.64	0.54–0.73
LAVI	1.00	0.98–1.02	0.830		
LAPS	1.11	1.02–1.22	0.017*		
Age	1.08	1.02–1.15	0.015*	0.65	0.56–0.74
Sex	0.60	0.29–1.24	0.171		
LARS	0.97	0.92–1.02	0.287		
Age	1.07	1.01–1.14	0.026*	0.69	0.59–0.78
Sex	0.59	0.29–1.21	0.147		
LAPS	1.10	1.01–1.20	0.037*		

Association with cardiovascular mortality in multivariable Cox regression analysis.

HR, hazard ratio; CI, confidence interval; LVEF, left ventricular ejection fraction; LAVI, left atrial volume index; LARS, left atrial reservoir strain; LAPS, left atrial pump strain.

* Significant values ($P < 0.05$).

Fig. 3. Comparison of model fit. Comparison of model fit of an echocardiographic model (A) and a clinical model (B).

*Significant values ($P < 0.05$).

χ^2 , chi-square; LVEF, left ventricular ejection fraction; LAVI, left atrial volume index; LARS, left atrial reservoir strain; LAPS, left atrial pump strain.

AS yielded very similar results. The data on all-cause death are shown in supplementary data online (Tables S3 – S6).

4. Discussion

This study demonstrates that in patients undergoing aortic valve replacement for severe AS 1) LAPS was reduced in individuals dying during long-term follow-up after TAVI; 2) LAPS was associated with mortality; 3) LAPS was an independent predictor of mortality; and 4) LAPS improved multivariable models with potential incremental value for association with mortality. In contrast, LARS was not significantly associated with long-term mortality nor useful for predicting outcome in this study population.

Severe AS induces cardiac remodelling, which is known to be associated with adverse survival [5]. The increased afterload is accompanied by structural and functional changes of both LV and LA [11,23]. With progressive AS, hypertrophy and fibrosis of LV myocardium becomes more pronounced and LV compliance declines leading to increased diastolic pressure with LA remodelling [6,24,25]. The resulting impairment of LA function contributes to deterioration in LV performance with decreased cardiac output [12]. Despite the potential relevance of these changes for long-term outcome, the most appropriate echocardiographic parameter indicating significant cardiac remodelling and thereby supporting the decision to intervene in patients with severe AS has not yet been defined.

Signs of chronic pressure exposure during the course of AS include an increase in LA size, which is evident in the current study population with late stage AS eligible for TAVI. LA strain is a promising indicator of adverse outcome offering incremental predictive value over clinical risk markers and conventional echocardiographic parameters in AS [26,27]. While more than three-quarters of the current study cohort exhibited an increased LAVI, less than a quarter of the study population had an altered LARS. This observation is in line with findings from previous research reporting no correlation between changes in LA size and LA function, emphasising that an increase in LA volume does not necessarily indicate an intrinsic LA dysfunction at least in terms of reservoir function even in patients with severe AS [28].

Published outcome studies in TAVI patients focus merely on LARS rather than LAPS [15,26,27,29–42]. In contrast to those studies, LARS was normal in the majority of the current study cohort, did not differ in patients with or without adverse outcome, and was not associated with outcome. This difference may be related to disease stage [26,27,30,35,37,41], disease management [26,27,29,30,35,41], endpoint definition [15,26,27,29–32,34–41] or follow-up duration [15,29,31,32,38,39]. To the best of our knowledge, two published studies have a similar design and the same endpoint as the current study. One of them was performed in cardiac computed tomography [33] and the other one included a baseline echocardiography performed after aortic valve replacement only [42]. Therefore, it is difficult to compare the LARS data from these reports with those of the current study. The lack of a statistically significant association of LARS with long-term outcome in the current study may be related to the normal LARS values in the majority of the population.

While LARS was not useful for the identification of patients at increased risk of death during follow-up, LAPS may be a promising parameter to gauge the extent of cardiac remodelling in response to severe AS. Since LAPS was associated with long-term outcome independently of conventional parameters such as LVEF and LAVI, and its association was much stronger than that of conventional parameters, it may be useful as a prognostic indicator after TAVI. Due to the phasic interactions between LV and LA during the cardiac cycle, the chronic increase in afterload occurring in AS affects not only the LV but also the LA [27]. The decreased LV compliance with increased LV diastolic pressure indeed leads to progressive LA dysfunction primarily compromising its contraction phase before a deterioration of reservoir or conduit phase occurs [16]. Consistent with this observation, the current

findings demonstrate that the decreased LAPS in patients with adverse outcome was neither driven by age nor sex. Hence, this functional deterioration seems to occur due to the severity of preinterventional aortic valve stenosis and to reflect the extent of associated cardiac damage [2,5,25,43]. Monitoring LA function in severe AS can thus provide valuable information on the extent of cardiac remodelling in response to valvular heart disease. Similar to LAEF, a decline in LARS may be considered a marker of global LA dysfunction [29], whereas a decline in LAPS indicates contractile LA dysfunction. The current data suggest that a decrease in LAPS may support the decision to replace the aortic valve even when LAEF and LARS are not altered significantly.

4.1. Clinical implications

Severe AS induces cardiac remodelling, which may indicate irreversible cardiac damage and be associated with adverse long-term outcome. LA strain is obtained from a non-foreshortened A4C or A2C view, which are routinely assessed in standard echocardiographic examinations. Impaired LAPS, but not LARS, indicates a higher probability of death during long-term follow-up after valve replacement for severe AS. Hence, LAPS should be determined in these patients and its reduced value should support the decision to replace the aortic valve for avoiding excessive cardiac remodelling and reduced outcome after intervention.

4.2. Limitations

A major limitation of this study is its retrospective single-center design. A selection bias cannot be excluded because inclusion criteria involved rigorous echocardiographic quality criteria as well as several additional clinical parameters. LA strain parameters were an important test variable used for Kaplan-Meier survival analyses based on an optimal threshold value, which was determined by ROC analysis in the same study population. Further multicenter studies and large-scale cohorts are necessary to validate the current findings.

5. Conclusion

In patients undergoing aortic valve replacement for severe AS, LAPS was impaired in patients dying during long-term follow-up after TAVI, differentiated survivors from non-survivors, was independently associated with long-term mortality, and yielded potential incremental value for survival prediction after TAVI. LAPS seems useful for risk stratification in severe AS and timely valve replacement.

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Disclosures

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2023.131403>.

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